

Species 1: *H. elevatus*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. numata*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.383

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

Species 1: *H. elevatus*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.3; high PNT

NDT test

Species 2: *H. numata*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.7; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1

Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.775

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.394$

Background 2->1

D
p.value = 0.00353

Background 1->2

D
p.value = 0.05263